

Gezi - 10 Years After, Maxim Gorki Theatre, 26 May - 25 June, 2023

Gezinema World Cinema Documentaries

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Co-curated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy and Necati Sönmez

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Screening: Your Turn, Eliza Capai, 2019

When Brazil's crisis deepened, students protested and occupied hundreds of schools, demanding better public education. The film depicts the Brazilian student movement from the protests of 2013 until the election of the new president, Jair Bolsonaro, in 2018. The documentary is narrated by three high school students, who represent central points of their struggle. The narrators' jostling for space exposes the movement's conflicts and complexity.

Q&A Session with Marlon Miguel, moderated by Şirin Fulya Erensoy

Marlon Miguel is Co-Principal Investigator at the project 'Madness, Media, Milieus. Reconfiguring the Humanities in Postwar Europe' at Bauhaus-Universität Weimar. He holds a double PhD in Fine Arts (Université Paris 8 Vincennes-Saint-Denis) and Philosophy (Federal University of Rio de Janeiro). He recently published *Camerling: Fernand Deligny On Cinema And The Image* (Leiden University Press, 2022). His current research focuses on the intersection between contemporary philosophy, art, anthropology, and psychiatry. He also practises contemporary circus and does practical movement research.

ŞE: Thanks everyone for sticking around. We hope you enjoyed the film. Before the film, there was a panel here and it was strategizing resilience and working with trauma so I was feeling a little vulnerable and sensitive, and this film re-energised and reminded me of the hope and beauty of collective action and youthful collective action at that. Anyway, I am here with Marlon Minguel. Marlon is a researcher, an academic and he is currently at the Bauhaus University in Weimar as the co-principal investigator at the project: Madness, Media, Milieu. Reconfiguring the Humanities in Post-war Europe. Marlon, thank you very much for being with us here today.

MM: Thank you.

ŞE: We are going to break down what is happening in the film. There is a lot of information and we are talking about a very long period starting from 2013. Some of the Turkish audience might remember the links in 2013 at Gezi where we opened Brazilian flags and so forth. In 2013, as far as I understand, the protests in Brazil started with the free fare movement. So there was a general unhappiness and revolt against the augmentation in transportation fees. How does this student movement relate to the general protest movements that were happening at the time

and how does it configure amongst other social movement groups that were active starting in 2013 but also perhaps with some references to the events of 2015 and 2016 that we see in the film.

MM: Thanks for the question and thanks for the invitation to this amazing programme. The festival is really beautiful and I appreciate what is being organised here. This period of Brazil is extremely complex but to try to answer your question - I would say that the student movement relates to a lot of other social movements. Two principal actors in this constellation could be mentioned: one is of course the free fare(MPL)

transport movement that is actually one that goes back to the beginning of the 2000s, founded during the World Social Forum of 2005, and with a very clear drive for the democratisation of public transport, urban mobility in especially huge monster cities like São Paulo. People generally spend 3-6 hours/day on public transport and it's expensive, and there is no such thing as a unified ticket that you can use for each connection, so everyone is paying a lot for each trip. Their idea was to propose complete free mobility in the city. In 2013, what happened is that the fare was increased by 20 cents but for most of the people, this was way too much and that was the beginning of this huge movement that came to be called 'The Journeys of June'. It started at the beginning of June and by the 20th, the peak moment, there were 1.2 million people on the streets. Most of the students that we see in the film, their first experiences with social movements, took place in that month of June. But most of the occupations we see in the film begin later in 2013 and until 2015. The second movement that was important in this context was the Homeless Workers Movement, the

MTST, whose leader we also see in the film, Guilherme Boulos. It is basically a movement for social housing, they occupy a lot of buildings, and are very active in the scene in São Paulo. I think they were also one of the triggers of the student's movement. I think we have to describe this student movement amongst these other social movements, particularly these two movements.

ŞE: But the student movement of and within itself is also not a singular movement, or movement that moves or acts together. In the Congress represented in the documentary, we saw that there were a lot of groups. Can you perhaps speak about these different groups? Do political parties have any influence on them, how are they organised and how do they relate to one another? In terms of how the information is relayed in the film, you have these 3 narrators who are bantering and casually talking about the movement, whether they agree or disagree. How does that relate to the divisions and commonalities between these different groups?

MM: The biggest parties in the political scenario usually have youth organisations. The Workers Party has one, the PSBD (the Social Democrats) do, the Socialists do... And you have the national student union movement (UNE), composed that is completely autonomous. Historically, the UNE was founded in the 1930s and is a very left-wing oriented movement. We had terrible and traumatic years of the dictatorship in Brazil from 1964-1985 and in the first terror days of the Dictatorship, the UNE main building was burned down, in Rio de Janeiro. The student movement is very diverse but the organisation is mostly left-oriented and comes from a history of social struggles and left-wing politics.

ŞE: The film ends with Bolsonaro's election where he makes quite frightening claims. He says: "We are going to end activism in Brazil." We leave the film off in 2019, then there's the pandemic, and then, Bolsonaro is not in power anymore. How have such developments since 2019 affect the student movement, its organisation and mobility?

MM: There is something very interesting and terrible that happened: there was a pushback against this activism, a resistance coming from the white bourgeois middle classes represented first by Michel Temer, who assumed the present position after the impeachment of Dilma Rousseff, and then Bolsonaro. The reaction to this activism became strangely organised by right-wing associations or organisations. There is one group in particular that proposed a project called Non-Partisan School. This came from the will to clear schools from political ideology, as these social and student movements, or in general the left-wing agenda was so present. This movement became very strong and Bolsonaro was of course one of the figures behind this and members around him were involved in this discourse. The statements were: let's clean schools from political activism, cultural marxism, gender ideology... Of course, lots of keywords were being used that are found in right-wing movements all over the globe but this was quite strong at this moment. The history of 2018-19 is very scary and now I would say, we are building a new movement starting again from ruins because these movements have been destroyed.

Q: The point at which you left, looking at the present and starting from scratch as the structures have been quite harmed during the Bolsonaro years. In the film, you also saw the left-wing presidency coincided with activism. What would be the prospects of a re-cohabitation, a left-wing presidency with a student movement in the universities or in general?

MM: I think co-existence would be possible again, which was completely impossible after the 2016 era and until now. The situation is far from simple. The governor of São Paulo back then is now the vice president of Lula. Just to give you a hint of how messy the situation is. This was a democratic alliance against fascism, so there was a real need to get rid of Bolsonaro and this whole far-right wing movement and alliance. For that there was this historical cohabitation alliance between this figure, Geraldo Alckmin (back then governor of São Paulo, during the students' movements and now vice-president) and Lula. Again, now we have the possibility of social activism, at least not to criminalise it the way it was criminalised the last few years both by politicians and by the media and by the police. I don't think it is going to be easy but at least there is no official criminalisation or there is this possibility of coexistence. We will see.

ŞE: There is more even-playing field to potentially rebuild. You mentioned the media, and at the end of the film there is a huge credit list of where the footage was taken, who had filmed what, etc. When we say media, in Turkey at least, and in relation to Gezi Park Protests, the media basically went into blackout mode, they didn't report on events, the famous penguin story¹, etc. and eventually when they could not ignore the protests anymore, the media spread propaganda, lying about what was happening in the park and what the protestors wanted. Obviously video activism, journalists, activists and documentary filmmakers started to proliferate because we needed to tell our own stories and nobody else was going to. So how did video activism affect the protests in Brazil and also help create this visual memory of what was happening, because we see this amazing footage at the epicentre of these protests, we see these students face very harsh police violence, we see them organise under very oppressive systems and we see them take action. Can you maybe talk a little bit about the media in this sense?

MM: I think 50% of the film's footage is from either independent media or video activists. Many of the students were filming with smartphones and this is part of the footage in the film. Media is one of the big issues. Before I came here today I looked for some data. There was a recent report from Media Ownership Monitor, which is an independent and serious research commission that looks into how media is organising material. 70% of open television in Brazil is controlled by four private groups. They function like the mafia. There is an appearance of independent, more or less official media, but the media is actually controlled by some families, and they are more interested in capital than in anything else. Basically what has been happening for decades is that the media is under the interest of capital, and it always has been like that. For instance, in 1964 during the military coup, most of the big media was supporting the coup and the same media was criminalising the Free Fare Movement, the student movements, and the very same media were also supporting the impeachment of Dilma Rousseff. So things are very intertwined and very complicated. Media activists play an important role in this whole movement because they open up the possibility of

¹ When protest broke out in Istanbul's Gezi Park in May 2013, and later spread to the rest of the country, Turkey's media went silent; as police brutality in Istanbul spiralled out of control on the night of Friday, 31 May 2013, CNN Türk chose to broadcast a documentary on penguins instead of informing the public about the events at Gezi Park. The penguin eventually became a symbol of resistance and media complicity; the image spread rapidly through social media, with people sharing photos, memes, and artwork featuring penguins as a form of protest.

constructing other narratives, but there is also a very strong right-wing video activism. Bolsanaro used alternative media - YouTube, WhatsApp, etc. There were a lot of people behind producing videos that were not in the mainstream or the official media.

Q: In the film we saw that people who went to work were annoyed by the protests of students who, by blocking highways for example, prevented people from going about their business. So do people support/are there networks of solidarity with the students and the workers? In Germany, now, for instance, we witness the criminalisation of climate activists in the media.

MM: I would say that these student movements were quite isolated, unfortunately. This was different from the June movement in 2013 where indeed there were a lot of working class movements that joined, or occupational movements, and even people who had no experience in politics of going on the streets, they were joining these huge movements. The media played a big role in pretty much criminalising the occupations and claiming that they were blocking the possibility or the access to study and to classes, and so on. I am pessimistic about the network of solidarity behind this movement, of course there was one, but it was minimal in comparison to other movements. We have a scene in the film from the Homeless Workers movement where they state that they will also occupy buildings or help in the occupation in the schools of the regions where they are active. For instance, this was one very strong movement that was connected to the school movement. Unfortunately, this was a rather isolated process.

SE: I have a comment. Thinking about the film, sometimes the images are so captivating you don't want to read the subtitles, and go with the energy but the discourse that these kids developed is incredible. They have this very real awareness of how sexism, racism, classicism works, and so they are very much aware and we see them developing discourse as they are getting organised, so they are learning as they are occupying, and this is so inspiring, and feels incredible that at 17 (maybe I am old school), they fully comprehend how the institution and the state apparatus work around them. Is this a new phenomenon, is this something that you would relate to this generation, or has the student movement been very proactive in the way they approach issues outside of education, such as: sexism, gender, racism and so forth?

MM: For me one of the most beautiful things in the film is indeed also seeing that fighting or the struggle itself is the means of learning. On the one hand, in the Brazilian context, yes, it is a generational thing. My generation, when we were in high school, we were discussing much less questions regarding gender, race and class. I also think it's related to what has been happening in Brazil since the beginning of the 2000s; there were lots of affirmative policies proposed by the Workers' Party. There was this policy of quotas, where people coming from public schools, and black and indigenous students would have a quota to enter the higher education system. There was a real agenda over these issues and these questions, and this has entered the discourse and the debates. It's generational, but it relates also to the politicisation process that we went through and waged these policies of the Workers' Party during the 2000s and 2010s. When we think about 2013, and then 2014-5 when things get more complicated because they are also captured by right-wing movements, in 2013 we see that it is not about radicalising the

democratisation process that was taking place thanks to these policies. What happened in 2013-14 is almost a reaction to this democratisation that had taken place. Things are very connected and it's amazing to see how good the young students are in discussing these issues.

SE: Thank you Marlon... Thank you so much for coming and have a good evening.

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